

On the Thiosulphato-tetrammine-cobaltic Series. Part II. Constitution of Duff's Salt.

BY BHABESH CHANDRA RAY AND PULIN BIHARI SARKAR.

By the action of barium thiosulphate on a hot solution of carbonato-diethylenediamine-cobaltic bromide Duff (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 450) obtained a thiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltic bromide to which he gave the following constitution evidently on

the assumption that S_2O_3 radical, divalent as it is, has substituted the CO_3 group and has taken up two contiguous co-ordination positions. This view on the constitution of the above salt was not substantiated by any other proof.

The present authors have prepared the sulphate and nitrate of this series firstly, by double decomposition of Duff's salt with Na_2SO_4 and KNO_3 and secondly, by the action of ethylenediamine on the corresponding *trans*-thiosulphato-aquo-tetrammine-cobaltic salts (Sarkar and Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 835). The products were identical and invariably contained water molecules in their composition.

Thus the sulphate was found to be $\text{Co}_2\text{En}_4(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and nitrate, $\text{Co En}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)(\text{NO}_3) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Two more salts of this series, namely the iodide and the thiocyanate have been prepared, having the molecular formulæ respectively,

The invariable presence of two molecules of water in the composition of the sulphate and one molecule in the composition of nitrate and iodide are rather significant.

These compounds do not lose any water on drying over H_2SO_4 in vacuum. It is difficult, *a priori*, to decide whether they are water of constitution or of crystallisation.

In order to decide this, we have taken recourse to analogy. Rây and his co-workers have prepared the compounds of thio-sulphato-pentammine-cobaltic ion (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 64) as well as isomeric thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltic acids and their salts (*ibid.*, 1927, **4**, 325 ; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, **199**, 353), where S_2O_3 radical has taken up one co-ordination position only.

Sarkar and Das-Gupta (*loc. cit.*) obtained, by the action of sodium thiosulphate on either *cis*-chloro-aquo or *trans*-dichloro-tetrammine cobaltic salts, *trans*-thiosulphato aquo-tetrammine series where also S_2O_3 radical was proved to occupy one co-ordination position.

By the action of sodium thiosulphate on *cis*- and *trans*- dichloro-diethylenediamine-cobaltic chlorides, the authors have obtained two isomeric dithiosulphato-diethylenediamino-cobaltates of sodium, the former in red-violet needles and the latter in green rhombic plates.

The constitution of these salts are apparent from their synthesis. They may be represented as :

In the above compounds thiosulphate radical has taken up, as is evident, only one co-ordination position. Molecular conductivity proves it to behave as a binary electrolyte.

The most interesting phenomenon observed in this case is the rapid transformation of the *cis* into *trans* modification, decidedly the stabler isomer. The transformation, in fact, was so rapid that the red-violet needles spontaneously changed into green plates even on exposure to air on microscope slides.

The *cis* variety was extremely hygroscopic and could only be kept in perfectly dry atmosphere.

The reciprocal transformation of green to red-violet salt can be effected in the following way:—The green solution is converted to pink red on adding NaOH from which by means of alcohol the red-violet salt can be obtained.

Rây and Maulik (*loc. cit.*) have simultaneously discovered these series by a totally different method (private communication).

We tried to prepare thiosulphato-complexes of the diammine series by the action of $Na_2S_2O_3$ on dichloro-diaquo-diamino-

cobaltic chloride where a green compound was obtained in which the ratio of Co : S was found to be approximately 8.3. The ratio is slightly high. All attempts to isolate the pure salt failed, the salt spontaneously decomposing. The sodium salt separates out as an oil on adding alcohol from which it gradually crystallises.

The ratio of Co : S (1 : 8.3) indicates the probable composition $\text{Na}_3 [\text{Co} (\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_4 (\text{NH}_3)_2], \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Evidently the thiosulphate radical has taken up one co-ordination position.

Moreover, the direct synthesis of Duff's salt from *trans*-thiosulphato-aquo-tetrammine-cobaltic salts and ethylenediamine speaks in favour of S_2O_3 occupying one co-ordination position. From the colour of the salt it may be inferred that it is a *cis* compound. In the acido-tetrammine and diethylenediamine series the *trans* compounds are generally green whereas the *cis* compounds are violet to red-brown. The present compound is red-brown.

Whatever may be its constitution, be it *cis*-thiosulphato-aquo as suggested by us or *cis*-thiosulphato as given by Duff, it should be, according to theory, resolvable into optically active antipodes.

In our attempt to resolve Duff's salt with *d*-bromocamphor sulphate as the active anion, we found the resulting sparingly soluble compound not to contain S_2O_3 radical. In fact, the co-ordinated S_2O_3 group is so very susceptible to hydrolysis that in course of double decomposition it comes out of the complex. This lends further support to our view that Duff's salt is a derivative of the monothiosulphato-aquo cation of the constitution

and not of $\left[\begin{array}{l} \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{En}_2 \\ 1:2 \end{array} \right]^+$ as supposed by Duff.

Salts of the sulphato-tetrammine series have not yet been prepared. Job (*Bull. Soc. chim. Belg.*, 1923, 33, 4) has definitely proved that the so-called sulphate-tetrammine series are really sulphato-aquo-tetrammine compounds.

Duff (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 52) claims to have prepared sulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltic bromide from $(\text{CO}_3 \text{Co En}_2)\text{Br}$ with H_2SO_4 .

The constitution proposed by him is $\left[\overline{\text{SO}_4} \text{Co En}_2 \right] \text{Br, H}_2\text{O}$.

The invariable presence of one molecule of water is significant. In the light of Job's work certainly it is sulphate aquo compound.

Theoretically, there should be another isomer of Duff's salt of the constitution

Attempts to isolate it were unsuccessful, only *cis* compound was obtained. Similar observations were made by Werner during his study of the chloro-aquo and bromo-aquo-diethylenediamine series, only the *cis* salts were isolated.

Thus, in view of the facts cited above, Duff's salt should be represented by the formula

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltic bromide (Duff salt) was prepared according to the direction of Duff (*loc. cit.*, p. 450) by the action of barium thiosulphate on carbonate diethylene-diamine-cobaltic bromide, prepared by the method of Werner (*Annalen.*, 1912, 386, 100).

Thiosulphato-aquo-diethylenediamine-cobaltic nitrate.—Duff's salt (4.25 g.) was dissolved in water (15 c.c.) and filtered, solid KNO_3 (2 g.) was added to the filtrate. On stirring and keeping in ice-bath dark-brown plates were obtained which were drained and washed with a little iced water. They were then recrystallised from water by evaporation in a vacuum over H_2SO_4 . The salt was washed with absolute alcohol and dried in the air, yield 1.2 g. (Found: N, 18.92; S, 17.29; Co, 15.95. $\text{Co}\cdot\text{S}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{En}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 18.87; S, 17.25; Co, 15.90 per cent).

Thiosulphato-aquo-diethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate.—Duff's salt (4.25 g.) was dissolved in 15 c.c. of water. To the clear solution of Na_2SO_4 (2 g.) was added and stirred while keeping in ice-bath.

Dark brown plates were obtained. They were then drained and recrystallised as before, yield 1 g. [Found: S, 22.35; Co, 16.56 ($\text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{En}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) $_2$ SO_4 requires S, 22.41; Co, 16.52 per cent].

Thiosulphato-diethylenediamine cobaltic-iodido.—Duff's salt (4.25 g.) was dissolved in the least quantity of water and finely powdered KI (1.7 g.) was added to the solution. Immediate precipitation of brown iodide took place. The mixture was stirred and kept in the ice-bath. After sometime the crystals were drained, washed first with a little ice water and then successively with 50% and 75% alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. The salt was recrystallised from water in a vacuum, yield 2.1 g. [Found: N, 12.82; I, 29.02; S, 14.52; Co, 13.57. ($\text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{En}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$)I requires N, 12.82; I, 29.12; S, 14.68; Co, 13.53 per cent.].

Thiosulphato-aquo-diethylenediamine-cobaltic thiocyanate.—Duff's salt (4.25 g.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and to it was added KSCN (1.5 g.). The mixture was kept in ice-bath. The crystals were drained, washed with dilute alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. They were then crystallised as before, yield 1.4 g. [Found: N, 18.0; S, 25.0; Co, 15.16. ($\text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{En}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) SCN, H_2O requires N, 18.18; S, 24.93; Co, 15.32 per cent].

Synthesis of Duff's salt from trans-thiosulphato-aquo-tetrammine-cobaltic bromide.—*trans*-Thiosulphato-aquo-tetrammine-cobaltic bromide (3.37 g.) prepared according to Sarkar and Das-gupta (*loc. cit.*) was treated with ethylenediamine solution (12 c.c. of 10%) and stirred. Strong smell of NH_3 was observed. After the elimination of NH_3 deep brown coloured plates were obtained. They were then drained, washed with a little iced water and finally with absolute alcohol. They were then recrystallised. [Found: N, 13.04; Br, 18.66; S, 15.19; Co, 13.80. ($\text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{En}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) Br, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 13.17; Br, 18.80; S, 15.09; Co, 13.88 per cent].

trans-Dithiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltate of sodium.—To an ice-cooled saturated solution of *trans*-dichloro-diethylenediamine cobaltic chloride (5 g.) a cold saturated solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (15 g.) was added. The mixture was kept in an ice-chest for 1 hour. The shining green plates were then drained, washed first with dilute alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. They are rhombic plates, soluble in water. [Found: N, 15.52; S, 29.86; Co, 13.78; Na, 5.54. $\{\text{Co} \cdot (\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot \text{En}_2\} \text{Na}$ requires N, 15.54; S, 30.04; Co, 13.85; Na, 5.39 per cent].

cis-Dithiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltate of sodium.—To an ice-cold saturated solution of *cis*-dichloro-diethylenediamine-cobaltic chloride (5 g.) was added a solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (15 g.) (made slightly alkaline with NaOH solution). The mixture was kept in an ice-bath. Red-violet needles separated, they were rapidly filtered, washed first with 50% and then with absolute alcohol. The salt was dried in a vacuum desiccator containing a little Am_2CO_3 . The red-violet needles on exposure to air spontaneously change into green plates at the ordinary temperature. [Found: N, 15.30; S, 29.91; Co, 13.80; Na, 5.26. $\text{Na Co}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2 \text{En}_2$ requires N, 15.54; S, 30.04; Co, 13.85; Na, 5.39 per cent].

Attempt to prepare tetrathiosulphato-diamine salts of cobalt.—To a well cooled solution of dichloro-diaquo-diamine-cobalt chloride, prepared according to Werner (*Ber.*, 1906 39, 1540) from Edmann's salt, was added a cold saturated solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (calculated amount). The mixture was kept in an ice-chest. Immediately on mixing a green scum separated. This was rapidly separated by filtration and to the cold filtrate an excess of cooled alcohol was added. A green oil separated which was removed by means of a separating funnel. It was redissolved in water and fractionated by means of alcohol. Finally the oil was crystallised on stirring with large excess of absolute alcohol.

On examination through microscope the salt appeared uniform. The salt is very unstable and begins to decompose when dry. The still moist salt was analysed. The ratio of Co : S was found to be 1 : 8.3. Qualitative analysis showed the presence of sodium and ammonia.

In any case, the ratio found corroborates the formation of tetrathiosulphato-diamine-cobaltate ion and strongly supports our views that S_2O_3 radical in complex cobaltamines takes up only one coordination position.